

ARCHITECTURAL OPTIMIZATION OF AES TRANSFORMATIONS AND KEYEXPANSION

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ABSTRACT

Advanced Encryption Standard (AES), is a cryptographic algorithm used for data protection. Designing an efficient hardware architecture for AES with small hardware resource usage is a challenge. Many works are going on for the efficient implementation of AES. The cost and power consumption of the AES can be reduced considerably by optimizing the architecture of AES. AES uses different data transformations such as AddRoundKey, SubByte, ShiftRow and MixColumn transformation and KeyExpansion block. In that, the two expensive transformations in terms of computational resources are MixColumns and SubBytes transformations. In this paper, new techniques for the ASIC implementation of the above transformations and KeyExpansion block are proposed.

KEYWORDS

AES, S-box, LUT, MixColumn, KeyExpansion

1. INTRODUCTION

The Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) can be used to provide security services such as data confidentiality or authentication. Data confidentiality provides protection of data from being disclosed by unauthorized parties. Data authentication is the assurance that the received data has not been replayed or affected by modification, insertion, or deletion, and also the sender is authenticated. AES was standardized by the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) in 2001[1]. NIST selected Rijndael as the proposed AES algorithm. Rijndael has many advantages. It has resistance against all known attacks. Hardware implementation has high speed. Compared to software implementation, the hardware implementation can achieve higher data rate for fast applications such as routers. The hardware implementation is also physically secure since tempering by an attacker is difficult [2]. The efficiency of AES hardware implementation in terms of size, speed, security and power consumption depends largely on the AES architecture [3]. AES has a wide range of applications such as secure networking routers, wireless communications, encrypted data storage including secure Smart Cards, secure video surveillance systems, secure RFID and electronic financial transactions. AES is a symmetric block cipher. Symmetric algorithms have one key. So both the sender and the receiver need to have the same key. A block cipher is a method of encrypting text in which a cryptographic key and algorithm are applied to a

block of data at once as a group rather than to one bit at a time. The specification of the AES block cipher, defines two functions: encryption that generates ciphertext and decryption that produces plaintext. The AES has a block length of 128 bits and key length of 128,192 or 256 bits. The basic unit of processing in the AES algorithm is a byte. The AES operates on a 4x4 array of bytes which is called a state. The state undergoes 4 transformations, namely the AddRoundKey, SubByte, ShiftRow and MixColumn transformation [1].

In AES, the two expensive transformations in terms of computational resources are MixColumns and SubBytes transformations [4]. This paper discuss few techniques to optimize these transformations and hence the algorithm.

2. AN INTRODUCTION TO AES

The AES algorithm operates on 128 bits of data and generates 128 bits of output. The length of the key used to encrypt this input data can be 128, 192 or 256 bits. As this is a symmetric key cipher it uses the same key for both Encryption and Decryption. N_b which defines the number of columns of 32 bits is, $N_b = 128/32=4$. Similarly N_k which defines the number of columns of 32 bits of key is, $N_k = 128/32= 4$. For key length of 192 and 256 the values of N_k will be $192/32= 6$ and $256/32= 8$ respectively. The number of rounds $N_r = 10$ when $N_k= 4$ and changes to 12 and 14 for $N_k =6$ and $N_k =8$ respectively. The key block round combinations are given in Table.1 [5]. As the key length is 128 bits i.e. $N_k = 4$, N_r will be 10.

Table .1 Key block round combination

	Key Length (N_k)	No.of columns (N_b)	No.of rounds (N_r)
AES-128	4	4	10
AES-192	6	4	12
AES-256	8	4	14

The AES algorithm basically consists of four byte oriented transformation and a key expansion function. The transformations are repeated for 10 rounds by applying the inputs to produce cipher text. For the first nine rounds all four blocks are repeated but for the final round the MixColumns transformations is excluded.

Figure.1 Basic building block of AES

The basic building block of AES containing four separate blocks, SubBytes, ShiftRows, MixColumns and AddRoundKey are shown in Figure.1 [6].

The AddRoundKey transformation involves a bitwise XOR operation between the state array and the resulting Round Key, which is derived from the initial key in the KeyExpansion function. SubByte transformation is a highly non-linear byte substitution where each byte in the state array is replaced with another from a lookup table called an S-Box. ShiftRow transformation is done by cyclically shifting the rows in the array with different offsets. Finally, MixColumn transformation is a column mixing operation, where the bytes in the new column are a function of the 4 bytes of a column in the state array.

3. INDIVIDUAL BLOCK DESCRIPTION

3.1. SubBytes

AES defines a 16×16 matrix of byte values, called an S-box [1] shown in Table.2. SubByte transformation is a nonlinear substitution that operates on individual bytes using a substitution table (S-Box), which contains a permutation of all 256 possible 8-bit values. Each individual byte of state is mapped into a new byte in the following way:

The left most 4-bits MSB of the byte are used as a row value and the rightmost 4-bits LSB are used as column value. These row and column value serve as indexes into the S-box to select a unique 8-bit output value. For example, the hexadecimal value {95} references row 9, column 5 of the S-box, which contains the value {2A}. Accordingly, the value {95} is mapped into the value {2A}.

Table.2 AES S-box

x/y	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	a	b	c	d	e	f
0	63	7c	77	7b	f2	6b	6f	c5	30	01	67	2b	fe	d7	ab	76
1	ca	82	c9	7d	fa	59	47	f0	ad	d4	a2	af	9c	a4	72	c0
2	b7	fd	93	26	36	3f	f7	cc	34	a5	e5	f1	71	d8	31	15
3	04	c7	23	c3	18	96	05	9a	07	12	80	e2	eb	27	b2	75
4	09	83	2c	1a	1b	6e	5a	a0	52	3b	d6	b3	29	e3	2f	84
5	53	d1	00	ed	20	fc	b1	5b	6a	cb	be	39	4a	4c	58	cf
6	d0	ef	aa	fb	43	4d	33	85	45	f9	02	7f	50	3c	9f	a8
7	51	a3	40	8f	92	9d	38	f5	bc	b6	da	21	10	ff	f3	d2
8	cd	0c	13	ec	5f	97	44	17	c4	a7	7e	3d	64	5d	19	73
9	60	81	4f	dc	22	2a	90	88	46	ee	b8	14	de	5e	0b	Db
a	e0	32	3a	0a	49	06	24	5c	c2	d3	ac	62	91	95	e4	79
b	e7	c8	37	6d	8d	d5	4e	a9	6c	56	f4	ea	65	7a	ae	08
c	ba	78	25	2e	1c	a6	b4	c6	e8	dd	74	1f	4b	bd	8b	8a
d	70	3e	b5	66	48	03	f6	e0	61	35	57	b9	86	c1	1d	9e
e	e1	f8	98	11	69	d9	8e	94	9b	1e	87	e9	ce	55	28	df
f	8c	a1	89	0d	bf	e6	42	68	41	99	2d	0f	b0	54	bb	16

S-Box is defined as the multiplicative inverse in the finite field $GF(2^8)$ with the irreducible polynomial $m(x)=x^8+x^4+x^3+x+1$ followed by an affine transformation. It can be constructed in the following fashion [1]:

1. Initialize the S-box with the byte values in ascending sequence row by row. The first row contains {00},{01},...,{0F}; the second row contains {10},{11}, etc. and so on. Thus, the value of the byte at row x, column y is {xy}.
2. Map each byte in the S-box to its multiplicative inverse in the finite field $GF(2^8)$; the value {00} is mapped to itself.
3. Consider that each byte in the S-box consists of 8-bits labelled $(b_7, b_6, b_5, b_4, b_3, b_2, b_1, b_0)$. Apply the following transformation Equation.1 to each bit of each byte in the S-box,

$$b'_i = b_{(i+4)\text{mod}8} \oplus b_{(i+5)\text{mod}8} \oplus b_{(i+6)\text{mod}8} \oplus b_{(i+7)\text{mod}8} \oplus c_i \tag{1}$$

where c_i is the i th bit of c with the value {63}; that is $(c_7c_6c_5c_4c_3c_2c_1c_0) = (01100011)$. The AES standard depicts this transformation in matrix form as shown in Equation.2.

$$\begin{pmatrix} b'_0 \\ b'_1 \\ b'_2 \\ b'_3 \\ b'_4 \\ b'_5 \\ b'_6 \\ b'_7 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} b_0 \\ b_1 \\ b_2 \\ b_3 \\ b_4 \\ b_5 \\ b_6 \\ b_7 \end{pmatrix} \oplus \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \tag{2}$$

In ordinary matrix multiplication, each element in the product matrix is the sum of products of the elements of one row and one column. In this case, each element is the bitwise XOR of the products of elements of one row and one column. As an example, consider the input value {95}. The multiplicative inverse in $GF(2^8)$ is $\{95\}^{-1} = \{8A\}$, which is 10001010 in binary. Using equation 1, the result will be {2A}, which should appear in row {09} column {05} of the S-box.

3.2 Shift Rows

ShiftRows essentially consists of shifting the bytes in the row. It is a transposition step on the row of the state where each row of the state is shifted cyclically by certain number of steps. The first row (row 0) is unaltered. The second row (row 1) is shifted by one byte, the third row is shifted by two bytes and final row is shifted three bytes. It also ensures that each byte in each row does not interact solely with their corresponding bytes. The transformation is shown in Figure.2.

Figure. 2 Row transformation

3.3 MixColumns

The MixColumns function takes four bytes as input and outputs four bytes, where each input byte affects all four output bytes. Together with ShiftRows, MixColumns provides diffusion in the cipher. Each column is treated as a polynomial over GF(2⁸) and is then multiplied modulo x⁴ + 1 with a fixed polynomial c(x) = {03} x³ + {01} x² + {01} x + {02}. During this operation, each column is multiplied by the known matrix and is shown in Equation.3.

$$\begin{pmatrix} S'_{0,c} \\ S'_{1,c} \\ S'_{2,c} \\ S'_{3,c} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 02 & 03 & 01 & 01 \\ 01 & 02 & 03 & 01 \\ 01 & 01 & 02 & 03 \\ 03 & 01 & 01 & 02 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} S_{0,c} \\ S_{1,c} \\ S_{2,c} \\ S_{3,c} \end{pmatrix} \quad (3)$$

0 c 4

The multiplication operation is defined as: multiplication by 1 means leaving unchanged, multiplication by 2 means shifting byte to the left by 1 position and multiplication by 3 means shifting to the left by 1 position and then performing xor with the initial unshifted value. After shifting, a conditional XOR with 11B should be performed if the shifted value is larger than xFF.

3.4 AddRoundKey

In the AddRoundKey transformation, a Round Key is added to the State by a simple bit wise XOR operation. Each Round Key consists of words from the key schedule. Those words are added into the columns of the state.

3.5 KeyExpansion

KeyExpansion generates a total of N_b(N_r + 1) words. The algorithm requires an initial set of N_b words, and each of the N_r rounds requires N_b words of key data. The resulting key schedule consists of a linear array of 4-byte words, denoted [w_i], with i in the range 0 ≤ i < N_b(N_r+1). The KeyExpansion has three steps: Byte Substitution subword(), Rotation rotword() and XOR with RCON (round constant). The subword() function takes a four byte input and applies the byte

substitution operation and produces an output word. The rotword() takes a word $[w_0, w_1, w_2, w_3]$ as input and performs a cyclic permutation to produce $[w_1, w_2, w_3, w_0]$ as output word. SubWord(RotWord(temp)) is XORed with Rcon[j] – the round constant. The round constant is a word in which the three rightmost bytes are zero. It is different for each round and defined as: $Rcon[j] = (RC[j], 0, 0, 0)$, where $RC[1] = 1$, $RC[j] = 2 * RC[j-1]$. Multiplication is defined over $GF(2^8)$. Values of $RC[j]$ in hexadecimal are shown in Table.3.

Table.3. Values of $RC[j]$

j	1	2	3	4	5	6
Rc[j]	01	02	04	08	10	20

The first N_k words of the expanded key are filled with the input key. With the help of these initial words, the rest of the 40 words are generated iteratively. It can be computed that, N_k is 4, 6, or 8, when the key length is 128, 192 or 256-bit, respectively. Each round key has 128 bits, and is formed by concatenating four words as shown in Equation.4.

$$\text{Roundkey}(i) = \{w_{4i}, w_{4i+1}, w_{4i+2}, w_{4i+3}\} \tag{4}$$

The structure of key expansion is shown in Figure.3 [5].

Figure.3 Data path for key expansion

4. RELATED WORK

4.1 S-Box

Traditionally, S-box was implemented by look up tables (LUT) [7] which store all 256 bit predefined values of S-Box in a ROM. The advantage of using LUT is it offers a shorter critical path. However, it has a drawback of the unbreakable delay in high speed pipelined designs, and hence it cannot be used in high speed applications. This delay prohibits each round unit from being divided into more than two sub-stages to achieve any further increase in processing speed. It also requires a large area to implement AES encryption and decryption system due to different table used for both systems.

The S-Box design uses combinational logic [8] to solve the unbreakable delay in look-up table. The S-box has 8 bit input and 8 bit output. It has 256 bit vectors having 128 ones and zeroes. The logic function to realize each byte is derived from the Boolean expression using k-map. Each input byte is represented as a,b,c,d,e,f,g and h. The 4 bit data input of least significant bit (LSB) will be the input of the sixteen module logic function (M1, M2, M3... M16) derived using Boolean simplification based on Karnaugh map. Another 4 bit data of most significant bit (MSB) will be the selection input of 16 to 1 multiplexer that will derive the output for S-box. Based on the MSB bits each module are selected. Each module in the architecture implies the rows in the S-box. The Boolean equation is derived for each row by taking the 4bit LSB as variables. This architecture can be used for SubByte Transformation. The S-Box architecture is shown in Figure.4.

Figure.4. Sbox architecture using combinational logic

4.2 MixColumns

In the AES algorithm, the MixColumns are hardware demanding operations. Various architectures have been proposed for the implementation of the MixColumns transformation. By analyzing the basic operations employed in MixColumns, it is found that the modular multiplier is the vital calculation module.

MixColumns can be implemented using a counter for shift operation. By using the counter the bytes of each column are shifted in each clock cycle. So it requires more clock cycle. The structure is shown in Figure.6 [9].

Figure.6 Structure of MixColumns using counter

$S_{i,c}$ are byte-format and assumed to be loaded into the multiplication register either in parallel or serial manner before the computation start. Data path is 8 bits wide. The computation of each transformed component takes one clock cycle. The next component can be computed with same set of data and multipliers. However, after the cyclic shift of $S_{i,c}$, i.e., $S_{i+1,c}$. As a result, the computation is a word-serial scheme. One column transform takes 4 clock cycles. The next data set will implement $S_{i,c+1}$. This method is suitable for compact system such as smart card and microcontroller based application [9].

The matrix multiplication of MixColumn could be represented as shown in equation.5 [10]. The function *xtime* is used to represent the multiplication with '02', modulo the irreducible polynomial $m(x) = x^8 + x^4 + x^3 + x + 1$. Implementation of function *xtime()* includes shifting and conditional XOR with '11B'.

$$\begin{aligned}
 b_0 &= \textit{xtime}(a_0 \oplus a_1) \oplus (a_0 \oplus a_1 \oplus a_2 \oplus a_3) \oplus a_0 \\
 b_1 &= \textit{xtime}(a_1 \oplus a_2) \oplus (a_0 \oplus a_1 \oplus a_2 \oplus a_3) \oplus a_1 \\
 b_2 &= \textit{xtime}(a_2 \oplus a_3) \oplus (a_0 \oplus a_1 \oplus a_2 \oplus a_3) \oplus a_2 \\
 b_3 &= \textit{xtime}(a_3 \oplus a_0) \oplus (a_0 \oplus a_1 \oplus a_2 \oplus a_3) \oplus a_3
 \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

From above representations, the MixColumn could be designed easily using just one basic module which imposes one *xtime* block, two or three byte-XOR logics and additional data path selector. This idea is depicted in Figure.5 [11]. The basic module of MixColumn is represented by the dashed line box in Figure.5. *xtime* module used in MixColumn can be implemented easily with combinations of XOR gates and hard-wired logic shift operation.

Figure.5 MixColumns and its basic module

4.3 KeyExpansion

The basic structure of the KeyExpansion uses four S-boxes for subword. Since S-box consumes more power, the number of S-box can be reduced to one. For each clock cycle the bytes from the rotword is given to S-box. So that only one S-box is needed at a time. The basic structure of KeyExpansion with one S-box is shown in Figure.7.

This structure is used for obtaining the first round key. Similar operations are repeated for the other rounds also. To optimize the power and area different techniques are introduced for KeyExpansion. A compact 32-bit datapath implementation of the key generation that can provide round keys for both encryption and decryption is proposed in [13]. This provides flexibility for applications where the cipher keys are frequently changed to enhance the security.

Figure.7 Basic structure of KeyExpansion

5. PROPOSED WORK

5.1 Implementation of S-Box

The major factors that influence the implementation techniques are speed and area cost. The efficiency of AES hardware implementation in terms of size, speed, security and power consumption depends mainly on the AES architecture. As S-Box is considered as a full complexity design and causes high power dissipation in AES [14], this paper is focused on the way to implement it efficiently.

In the proposed technique 16×16 S-box is divided into four blocks. Each block consists of 8×8 S-box with 64 values in each blocks. The blocks are selected using a 4:1 multiplexer. In S-box the 4-bit MSB is represented in the row and 4-bit LSB is represented in column. To select each block, the first MSB bit and first LSB bit is taken. These bits are given as select line input to the multiplexer. If the select line is 00, the left half of the upper part of the S-box is selected. The right half is selected when the select line is 01. Similarly, the lower left and right part is selected when the select line is 10 and 11 respectively. The structure [12] for this method is shown in Figure.9.

Figure.9. Structure of S-box using MUX

5.2 Implementation of MixColumn

In the proposed method, the MixColumn is implemented using multiplexer based on the matrix form. The structure is used for four columns operation for 128 bit input. Five 4:1 multiplexer are used in this structure. This is used to shift the bytes in each column. The structure using multiplexer for MixColumn is shown in Figure.10.

Figure.10 Structure using MUX for MixColumn

As explained in section 3.3, in the MixColumn transformation each byte from the multiplexer will be multiplied with 2, 3 or 1 respectively based on the matrix given in Equation.3. In the proposed method instead of shifting the fixed coefficient, the input bytes are shifted. The matrix is given in Equation.6. Based on the select lines the multiplexer select each word. When the select line is “00”, the MUX selects $\{S_{0,c}, S_{1,c}, S_{2,c}, S_{3,c}\}$ and it will multiplied by the corresponding coefficient. When the select line is “01” the word will be shifted by one byte, $\{S_{1,c}, S_{2,c}, S_{3,c}, S_{0,c}\}$. The operation, thus continues for other select lines. By shifting the bytes in each column the multiplication with values 2 and 3 in the matrix can be reused. So that the area can be optimised. Because the state of AES algorithm consist byte of arrays, the most operations could be processed by unit of byte.

$$\begin{pmatrix} S'_{0,c} \\ S'_{1,c} \\ S'_{2,c} \\ S'_{3,c} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} S_{0,c} & S_{1,c} & S_{2,c} & S_{3,c} \\ S_{1,c} & S_{2,c} & S_{3,c} & S_{0,c} \\ S_{2,c} & S_{3,c} & S_{0,c} & S_{1,c} \\ S_{3,c} & S_{0,c} & S_{1,c} & S_{2,c} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 2 \\ 3 \\ 1 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (6)$$

5.3 Implementation of KeyExpansion

The proposed work to optimize the KeyExpansion is based on multiplexer. The structure is given in Figure.11. In this structure one 2:1 multiplexer and one 4:1 multiplexer is used. The 4:1 multiplexer is used to select each word to be XORed. The fourth byte W3 undergoes the functions such as rotword, subword and rcon respectively and is given to 2:1 multiplexer as one input. If the select line of 4:1 multiplexer is “00”, W0 will be selected and is XORed with the output byte of 2:1 multiplexer when the select line is “0”, ie, with W3 in which rotword, subword and rcon takes place. This XORed byte is given as the other input for the 2:1 multiplexer and will be selected when the select line is “1”. Similarly, if the select line is “01”, “10” and “11”, W1, W2, and W3 will be selected respectively. This structure is repeated for all rounds.

Figure.11 Proposed structure for KeyExpansion

6. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The design of AES transformations was done in Verilog HDL. The power and area are analyzed using Synopsys Design Vision. 90nm technology was used. Design Vision is RTL Synthesis tool by Synopsys. RTL synthesis is an automated design task in which high-level design descriptions written in Hardware Description Languages such as VHDL, Verilog, or SystemVerilog are transformed into gate-level netlists. Gate-level netlist is basically a circuit implementation of the design made of library components (both combinational and sequential cells) available in the technology library and their interconnections. The netlist is generated by the synthesis tool according to the constraints set by the designer.

6.1 Results for S-Box implementation

The power and area can be found using Synopsys tool. The result on Synopsys is shown in Table.3. It is clear that the multiplexer logic has less power consumption. The area can be reduced by combinational method, but the power is very high. So the multiplexer method was found to be the optimized technique.

Table.3 Results for Subbyte

Type	Area (μm^2)	Power (μW)
LUT	2146	57.21
Combinational logic	728	121.8
MUX	848	54.81

Using the proposed, splitting logic of S-box, the power is reduced than the traditional LUT method.

6.2 Results for MixColumns implementation

In the multiplexer method of MixColumn, the design is proposed which uses less hardware. The MixColumn with multiplexer is having less area and low power consumption. The different MixColumns implementation using xtime [8] and counter [7] was also implemented and it was compared with the proposed work. The result is given in Table.4.

Table.4. Results for MixColumn

Type	Area (μm^2)	Power (μW)
Basic	1296	225.5
xtime	1399	315.43
Counter	1168	123.6
MUX	879	32.29

The proposed multiplexer method was having 85% reduction in power than the basic method.

6.3 Results for KeyExpansion implementation

The result is shown in Table.5. The proposed method is optimised for power. The power consumption is less for the proposed method. The basic method is having less area, but the power is higher than the proposed technique.

Table.5. Results for KeyExpansion on Synopsys

Type	Area (μm^2)	Power (μW)
Basic	2625	137.1
Proposed	2889	53.3

From the results given in the Table.5, it was clear that, there was 61% reduction in power than the basic technique. Thus, an optimized ASIC implementation design of SubByte, MixColumns transformation and KeyExpansion was implemented. With these optimised techniques of SubByte, MixColumn and KeyExpansion, a compact AES architecture can be developed.

7. CONCLUSION

The proposed design was optimized for power. The design is modelled using Verilog HDL. The transformations and KeyExpansion provides the smallest hardware usage on ASIC due to the efficient resource sharing. Hardware implementation has high speed. It is also physically secure since tempering by an attacker is difficult. Thus the overall AES encryption implementation with the proposed architecture reduces usage of hardware resources. The proposed design can be used to provide security services such as confidentiality or authentication.

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